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Least Mastered Reading Skills of Grade 7 Students: Basis for Developing Enhancement Material in English

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Abstract

The study attempted to develop and evaluate enhancement reading material in English 7 for the students of San Roque National High School, District II-B of Antipolo City during the School Year 2017–2018. The descriptive method of research with the survey questionnaire, as its main data gathering instrument, was used. Based on the findings, there were ten (10) least mastered reading skills in English 7 which served as the basis for the development of enhancement material. In addition, the English teachers and the experts evaluated the developed enhancement reading material based on its parts: overview, learning objectives, learning content, practice task and assessment as Moderately Agree with average means of 4.42 and 4.35 respectively. More so, the readability level of the literatures on the developed enhancement reading material based on Flesch's reading formula was appropriate to Grade 7 students as regards the reading ease score of 76.8 and 83.1 respectively. It was concluded that the developed enhancement reading material in Grade 7 English is practical for actual use of English teachers in Grade 7 level. Also, the evaluations of the two groups of respondents on the developed enhancement reading material in Grade 7 English do not vary from each other. Furthermore, it was recommended that the developed enhancement reading material in Grade 7 English may be validated to determine their effectiveness for better performance of the students.

Keywords: *least mastered reading skills, enhancement material, english 7*

Introduction

Reading is a habit where students learn, gain knowledge and develop new skill. Understanding the significance of reading and in line with the implementation of the K to 12 Basic Education Program, the Department of Education (DepEd) implemented "Every Child A Reader Program" (ECARP), through DepEd Memorandum No. 402. s. 2004 and Administrative Order No. 324 aims that all students must learn to read. Thus, the Department of Education (DepEd) envisions to lead the young Filipino learners in the discovery of their own potential and for the promotion of their values and competencies to create their own path, to contribute meaningfully in nation-building, and to train them to instill positive change to the global community.

Literacy demands on students present and in the future are for proficient and advanced reading ability. It is the dream of every educator that every learner develops the core requirements in terms of knowledge, skills and understandings, and transfer learning automatically and flexibly to combat the challenges of life and the demands of the society. Learning to read is, without question, the main concern. Through reading, one obtains access to knowledge in the different learning areas. Conversely, if a person fails to master the desired competencies in reading, he is deprived of this privilege. The United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO 2011) asserts that being able to read is not enough measure to be literate in reading. Rather, one must understand or comprehend what he reads; applies, integrates, and synthesizes. But how could a learner be able to understand the printed symbols if he has not acquired the proper reading and thinking ability?

Everyone owes things to reading. How could one meet Shakespeare, J.K. Rowling and Alexander Dumas if it is not in reading? How could one know that Galileo Galilee was the one who invented telescope if reading materials were not provided? How could one appreciate other countries and their culture if written text were not found and put in the books? Moreover, how could one know the current events on their surroundings if newspapers and magazines that bring fresh bits of information were not printed?

Indeed, through reading people can acquire many things. That is why a lot of reading programs are conducted in every school to enhance students' comprehension. In learning institutions, there is always a need to intensify renewed efforts as well as commitment in promoting and sustaining effective reading skills even more in today's rapidly changing conditions (Hontiveros, 2018). Despite it all, why is poor reading comprehension still visible among the students? These questions have caught the attention of the researcher. The country is eyeing these youngsters as its future citizens. That is what is being connoted in the well-known Filipino-slogan: "And kabataan ang pag-asa ng bayan". So, it is necessary for her to meet the needs of these future defenders of the country. Education is one of their basic needs. Therefore, it is a must for those who are in charge in this area, to give them the quality of education. The success of the school nowadays is judged by its pupils' proficiency in reading. This is the reason why the Department of Education dreams of producing learners who are effective readers upon completion of third grade by launching the "Every Child A Reader Program" (ECARP) and the "Bright Child Program".

Poor reading comprehension is not a mortal sin for the students; it is not just but inability on their part. They should not be the one to suffer. It is the burden of the teachers. The development of the students still counts more on the effectiveness of their instructional material.

As a language teacher and a student pursuing master's degree, this problem bothers her so much that leads her in choosing the topic. Secondly, it is for her to contribute and conceptualize an enhancement material to aid the deficiency of students in terms of reading. With this, the researcher insisted that there is really a need to pursue this study.

Research Questions

This study attempted to develop and evaluate enhancement reading material in English for Grade 7 students in San Roque National High School, San Roque, Antipolo City during the School Year 2018-2019. Specifically, it sought answers to the following questions:

1. What were the least mastered skills in Reading of Grade 7 students based on their School Achievement Test which were developed into an enhancement reading material in English?
2. What was the evaluation of the expert and teacher respondents on the developed enhancement materials in English as regards to the following aspects?
 - 2.1. overview;
 - 2.2. learning outcomes;
 - 2.3. learning content;
 - 2.4. practice task; and
 - 2.5. assessment?
3. Was there a significant difference between the evaluations of the experts and teacher respondents as regards the developed enhancement materials in English?
4. What was the reading readability level of the reading text in the developed enhancement materials using the Flesch's formula?
5. What were the comments and suggestions offered by the two groups of respondents to improve the developed enhancement materials in English?

Literature Review

Reading takes an international significance nowadays. With the global demand for literacy, reading at present becomes the most strategic means of promoting welfare and international welfare.

Sanjran (2013) emphasized that reading skills are essential to succeed in society. Those who are good readers tend to exhibit progressive social skills. A person who is widely read is able to mix with others. He is a better conversationalist than those who do not read. He can stand his ground. Reading broadens the vision.

In addition, Martinez (2014) stated that reading plays a vital role in the life of a man. Without the ability to read, a person will never have one of the most valuable tools for learning in the real sense; the ability to read is an essential element in every person to enable him to cope in the real world today. When students fail to improve literacy skills in young age, they are more likely to struggle throughout their academic careers and it's time-intensive and expensive to remediate their difficulties. Poor reader students in early grades rarely catch up to their peers, even with extra help, putting them at risk for learning difficulties and various negative educational outcomes. A good reader can interact with others in a far better way because reading has widened his vision and point of view. Thus, a widely-read man is a better conversationalist and is able to see the other side point of view.

Wabuke (2013) noted that encouragement of teachers is needed in the regular assessment of the learners on practical skills. Perhaps, further availability and documentation on practical lessons is adhered to for planning teachers and regular inspection to actual order insurance. School plays a valuable and significant role in promoting the reading habits, making extensive use of books, not just textbooks, but also other reading materials.

As cited by Rulp (2014), he mentioned that remedial reading instruction is more intensive and more specialized than corrective instruction. Students who have remedial problem read below their expected level. Furthermore, remedial reading is most often taught by reading resource teacher in a special school. Remedial procedures employed by any teacher of reading must take into account the unique characteristics of the students' learning situation.

According to the case study of Vogel (2013), reading interventions were necessary for many students, yet many school sites and school districts adopted programs and strategies for general populations rather than specific students which supported the need for research. Teachers were the most critical element in the success of student achievement. For example, most educators have tracked students' progress as content was learned in order to make them successful with subject matter. More specifically, they focused on "learning goals, attended to the integrity of the subject matter, managed individual student behavior and maintained a productive learning environment, posed strategically targeted questions, interpreted students' work, crafted responses, assessed, and steered all of this toward each students' growth.

Relatively, Fuchs (2014) posited that regularly collected progress monitoring data provides the objective information teachers need to document student skill development and evaluate intervention efficacy. In this study, the researcher used the test result of the students to objectively assess the students' reading deficiency.

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instruction. Students who have remedial problem read below their expected level. Furthermore, remedial reading is most often taught by reading resource teacher in a special school. Remedial procedures employed by any teacher of reading must take into account the unique characteristics of the students' learning situation.

Methodology

Research Design

This study used the descriptive normative method of research. According to Calderon and Gonzales (2009), this is a fact-finding study with adequate and accurate interpretation. This was used to collect data about the people's behavior, practices, intentions, beliefs, attitudes, opinions, interests, perceptions, and the like and then such data are analyzed, organized and interpreted. The descriptive normative survey was used to determine the significant difference between the evaluations of the expert and the Reading teacher respondents on the developed supplementary reading material.

Respondents

The respondents involved in this study were 30 reading teachers, and 15 experts. The expert teachers refer to the group composed of Master Teachers (MT), Department Heads, Head Teachers, Subject Coordinators, School Principals, and Education Program Supervisors knowledgeable in English pedagogy and instruction.

Instrument

Documentary analysis was utilized to determine the least mastered skills in reading based on the School Achievement Test for school year, 2017-2018.

For the evaluation of the developed enhancement reading material, the researcher used the researcher-made questionnaire-checklist. The evaluation questionnaire was validated by expert teachers and the researcher's adviser. The study also made use of Flesch's Reading Formula in order to determine the readability score of the literary texts used in the enhancement material. This was used to see if the literary texts were suitable and appropriate to the level of the target learners. The developed enhancement material in reading was evaluated based on its parts: overview, learning objectives, learning content, practice task and assessment. Each criterion has sub-characteristics which were rated according to the general guideline for each category.

Procedure

The researcher secured first permission from the Schools Division Superintendent of Antipolo City to conduct this research study and to the principal of the schools where the study was conducted. The researcher made use of a document analysis of the areas of the difficulties in Reading based from the results of the School Achievement Test. Using the least mastered skills in Reading, the researcher developed enhancement reading material as the main gathering tool. After the ten least mastered skills were identified, the texts that were included were selected based on its readability score. The researcher made use of the Flesch's Reading Formula. After the development of the enhancement material in reading, distribution of the developed material to the expert teachers and teachers of English was conducted for the evaluation of the developed material based on its parts: overview, learning objective, learning content, practice task, and assessment. The researcher used a cover letter addressed to the respondents who gave their time and expertise in scrutinizing the material. The evaluations of the two groups of respondents were collected and submitted through statistical analysis of data.

Results and Discussion

This portion presents the results and discussion based on the gathered data.

Least Mastered Skills in Reading of Grade 7 Students Based on the School Achievement Test in San Roque National High School, SY 2017-2018 which Were Developed into Enhancement Materials in English

Table 1. *Computed Mean and Rank of the Result of Least Mastered Learning Competencies in Grade 7 English Based on the School Achievement Test*

	<i>Skills/Competencies</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Rank</i>
1.	Differentiate reality from fantasy.	45.40	1
2.	Predict outcomes.	36.75	2
3.	Identify the meaning of unfamiliar words through contextual clues.	33.93	3
4.	Make inferences from the text read.	31.12	4
5.	Identify the features of proverbs, their intended purpose, and setting during which they were produced.	30.03	5
6.	Identify the topic sentence.	28.73	6
7.	Determine author's technique for characterization.	24.42	7
8.	Determine tone, mood and theme of a literary piece.	24.42	8
9.	Identify the different types of paragraphs.	20.92	9
10.	Distinguish the sensory images used.	19.78	10

It can be gleaned on Table 2 that the skill or competency, differentiating reality from fantasy, has the highest computed mean of 45.40 and occupies the first rank. While placing in the second, third, fourth, fifth, sixth, seventh, eighth, ninth, and tenth ranks are the following skills/competencies: predict outcomes, identify the meaning of unfamiliar words through context clues; make inferences from the text read; identify the features of proverbs; identify the topic sentence; determine the author’s technique for characterization; determine tone, mood and theme of a literary piece; identify the different types of paragraph; and distinguish the sensory images used, respectively.

This implies that the aforementioned ten skills or learning competencies for school achievement test were determined as difficult topics or competencies for the students since they lack the prior knowledge of these skills as evidenced by the scores presented on the table. These topics/ competencies have to be prioritized and be given emphasis inside the classroom through the use of enhancement reading material in order for the students not just to learn the concepts or competencies but to use and apply it in meaningful contexts or situations.

Evaluation of the Experts and Teacher Respondents on the Developed Enhancement Materials in English

Table 2. Respondents’ Evaluations on the Developed Enhancement Materials in English Regarding Overview

		<i>The overview:</i>			
		<i>Teachers</i>		<i>Experts</i>	
		<i>WM</i>	<i>VI</i>	<i>WM</i>	<i>VI</i>
1.	Is clearly and precisely stated.	4.37	MA	4.20	MA
2.	Is related to the contents and reading text.	4.40	MA	4.40	MA
3.	States the character that is hoped to be developed among students.	4.30	MA	4.00	MA
4.	Uses language that is basic, simple and easy to comprehend.	4.53	SA	4.33	MA
5.	Provides the learners background of information about topics to be studied	4.50	SA	4.27	MA
Overall Weighted Mean		4.42	MA	4.24	MA

It can be observed in Table 2 that the teacher respondents’ evaluation on the developed English Enhancement reading material regarding overview is Strongly Agree in indicators 4 and 5 as evidenced by the weighted means of 4.53 and 4.50, respectively. To sum, both group of respondents rated the overview as Moderately Agree as evidenced by the overall weighted means of 4.42 and 4.24, respectively. According to the teacher respondents, the overview of the developed English Enhancement Reading Material for the students uses language that is basic, simple and easy to comprehend. It also provides the learners background information about the topics to be studied.

It implies that the overview in the developed enhancement reading material for English is easy to comprehend and it provides sufficient background information to the students. The overview is stated in a way that it could be understood by its readers.

Table 3. Respondents’ Evaluations on the Developed Enhancement Materials in English Regarding Learning Outcomes

		<i>The learning outcomes:</i>			
		<i>Teachers</i>		<i>Experts</i>	
		<i>WM</i>	<i>VI</i>	<i>WM</i>	<i>VI</i>
1.	Are presented in specific way.	4.33	MA	4.47	MA
2.	Lead the students to think critically.	4.47	MA	4.40	MA
3.	Are attainable by the students.	4.40	MA	4.53	SA
4.	Are result-oriented.	4.30	MA	4.53	SA
5.	Are assessable.	4.43	MA	4.33	MA
Overall Weighted Mean		4.39	MA	4.45	MA

It can be seen in Table 3 that both group of respondents rated Moderately Agree the first two indicators as well as the last indicator as evidenced by the weighted means of 4.33 and 4.47; 4.47 and 4.40; and 4.43 and 4.33, respectively. To sum, both group of respondents rated the learning outcomes as Moderately Agree as evidenced by the overall weighted means of 4.39 and 4.45, respectively. Nevertheless, both group of respondents rated Strongly Agree for indicators which stated that the learning outcomes are attainable by the students and are result-oriented as evidenced by the weighted means of 4.40 and 4.53 and 4.30 and 4.53, respectively.

It implies that the learning outcomes in the developed enhancement reading material for English are achievable by the students and are result-oriented.

It can be gleaned on Table 4 that the experts and English teacher respondents’ evaluation on the developed English Enhancement Reading Material regarding the content is Moderately Agree as evidenced by the overall weighted means of 4.48 and 4.49, respectively. Based from the two groups of respondents, the content part of the developed enhancement reading material is rated Strongly Agree for indicators 1 and 3 which stated that the content is significant and appropriate to the needs of the students and simple and comprehensive as evidenced by the weighted means of 4.63 and 4.53; 4.50 and 4.53, respectively.

It implies that the developed enhancement reading material is simple with proper and comprehensive language in order for the students to read it with ease, and presented illustrations and examples suitable to the needs of the students can see the material not a burden.

Table 4. Respondents' Evaluations on the Developed Enhancement Materials in English Regarding Learning Content

	The learning content:		Teachers		Experts	
			WM	VI	WM	VI
	1. Is significant and appropriate to the needs of the students.	4.63	SA	4.53	SA	
2. Have topics that are relevant, interesting, self-motivating, and at the level of understanding of the students.	4.43	MA	4.47	MA		
3. Is simple and comprehensive.	4.50	SA	4.53	SA		
4. Provides different lessons that support the attainment of set objectives.	4.43	MA	4.47	MA		
5. Activates students' prior knowledge which is evident in every topic.	4.40	MA	4.47	MA		
Overall Weighted Mean			4.48	MA	4.49	MA

Evident on Table 5 is the summary of the evaluations of the two groups of respondents' evaluations on the practice task of the developed enhancement reading material in English for Grade 7 students. It can be gleaned in the table that the experts and English teacher respondents regarding the practice task is Moderately Agree as evidenced by the overall weighted means of 4.40 and 4.29, respectively.

Table 5. Respondents' Evaluations on the Developed Enhancement Materials in English Regarding Practice Task

	The practice task:		Teachers		Experts	
			WM	VI	WM	VI
	1. Gives clear direction and information about the activities.	4.47	MA	4.27	MA	
2. Helps students understand better and recall more easily the concepts discussed.	4.47	MA	4.27	MA		
3. Arouses the students' interest and motivates the students.	4.40	MA	4.20	MA		
4. Shows that the sequence of difficulty for the activities is well organized.	4.30	MA	4.33	MA		
5. Includes illustrations for the activities that are well presented.	4.37	MA	4.13	MA		
Overall Weighted Mean			4.40	MA	4.24	MA

It shows that experts and teacher respondents have the same evaluation regarding the practice task of the developed enhancement reading material.

Table 6. Respondents' Evaluations on the Developed Enhancement Materials in English Regarding Assessment

	The assessment:		Teachers		Experts	
			WM	VI	WM	VI
	1. Takes into account the attitudes and abilities of the students.	4.37	MA	4.27	MA	
2. Uses language and style that are appropriate to the ability of the students.	4.47	MA	4.33	MA		
3. Is presented clearly and captivating.	4.47	MA	4.33	MA		
4. Makes students clearly chart their progress on various skills.	4.37	MA	4.27	MA		
5. Is congruent to the learning outcome.	4.47	MA	4.47	MA		
Overall Weighted Mean			4.43	MA	4.33	MA

As reflected in Table 6, the teacher respondents have similar evaluation with the experts as both groups rated all the indicators Moderately Agree as shown by the overall weighted means of 4.43 and 4.33, respectively. This suggests that the developed enhancement material contains activities that evaluate the performance of the target users after being exposed its content.

It implies that the developed reading material can be utilized to assess the learner's performance after its utilization to identify their level of mastery of the prescribed competencies.

Significant Difference Between the Evaluation of the Experts and Teacher Respondents on the Developed Enhancement Materials in English

Table 7. Test of Difference Between the Evaluations of the Two Groups of Respondents on the Developed Enhancement Materials in English Regarding Overview

Respondents	WM	S	Computed t Value	Critical t Value ($\alpha=5\%$, $df=43$)	Decision	Interpretation
Experts	4.24	0.43	0.96	2.02	Fail to Reject the Ho	Not Significant
Teachers	4.42	0.66				

As displayed in Table 7, the critical t value is 2.02 with 43 degrees of freedom, and the computed t value is 0.96. Since the computed t value is less than the critical t value, at the 5% level of significance, the statistical decision is not to reject the null hypothesis. Hence, there is no significant difference between the evaluations of the two groups of respondents on the developed enhancement materials in English in terms of overview.

This implies that the overview of the developed enhancement material is clearly and precisely stated. It also provides background information about the topics to be studied. Thus, overview part made use of a language that is comprehensible and logical to its users.

Concise and explicit language is used so that the learners could grasp the statements correctly without any second thought and inhibitions.

Table 8. *Test of Difference Between the Evaluations of the Two Groups of Respondents on the Developed Enhancement Materials in English Regarding Learning Outcomes*

Respondents	WM	S	Computed t Value	Critical t Value ($\alpha=5\%$, $df=43$)	Decision	Interpretation
Experts	4.45	0.45	0.30	2.02	Fail to Reject the Ho	Not Significant
Teachers	4.39	0.79				

In Table 8, as the computed t value of 0.30 is lower than the critical t value of 2.02, at the 5% level of significance, the statistical decision is not to reject the null hypothesis. Hence, there is no significant difference between the evaluations of the two groups of respondents on the developed enhancement materials in English in terms of learning outcomes.

It implies that the learning outcomes in the developed enhancement reading material for English are achievable by the students and are result-oriented.

Table 9. *Test of Difference Between the Evaluations of the Two Groups of Respondents on the Developed Enhancement Materials in English Regarding Learning Content*

Respondents	WM	S	Computed t Value	Critical t Value ($\alpha=5\%$, $df=43$)	Decision	Interpretation
Experts	4.49	0.48	0.08	2.02	Fail to Reject the Ho	Not Significant
Teachers	4.48	0.56				

As presented in Table 9, the computed t value of 0.08 is below the critical t value of 2.02, then the statistical decision is not to reject the null hypothesis. At the 5% level of significance, it means that there is no significant difference between the evaluations of the two groups of respondents on the developed enhancement materials in English in terms of learning content.

This implies that the developed enhancement reading material is simple with proper and comprehensive language in order for the students to read it with ease, and presented illustrations and examples suitable to the needs of the students can see the material not a burden.

Table 10. *Test of Difference Between the Evaluations of the Two Groups of Respondents on the Developed Enhancement Materials in English Regarding Practice Task*

Respondents	WM	S	Computed t Value	Critical t Value ($\alpha=5\%$, $df=43$)	Decision	Interpretation
Experts	4.24	0.49	0.74	2.02	Fail to Reject the Ho	Not Significant
Teachers	4.40	0.76				

The computed t value of 0.74 in Table 10 is less than the critical t value of 2.02, so the statistical decision is not to reject the null hypothesis. It means that at 5% level of significance, there is no significant difference between the evaluations of the two groups of respondents on the developed enhancement materials in English in terms of practice task.

This means that the practice task gives clear direction and information about the activities. Thus, it helps the students understand between and recall more easily the concepts discussed.

Table 11. *Test of Difference Between the Evaluations of the Two Groups of Respondents on the Developed Enhancement Materials in English Regarding Assessment*

Respondents	WM	S	Computed t Value	Critical t Value ($\alpha=5\%$, $df=43$)	Decision	Interpretation
Experts	4.33	0.49	0.53	2.02	Fail to Reject the Ho	Not Significant
Teachers	4.43	0.58				

As shown in Table 11, the computed t value of 0.53 is lower than the critical t value of 2.02, then the statistical decision is not to reject the null hypothesis. At the 5% level of significance, it concludes that there is no significant difference between the evaluations of the two groups of respondents on the developed enhancement materials in English in terms of assessment.

This implies that the assessment takes into account the attitude and abilities of the students. It is also evident that it is congruent to the learning outcomes.

Table 12. *Readability Level of the Developed Enhancement Materials Using the Flesch's Formula*

Title of The Literary Text	Flesch Reading Ease Score	Interpretation	Grade Level
Magnificence	76.8	Fairly Easy to Read	7
The Summer Solstice	83.1	Easy to Read	7

This affirms the implications that the reading texts found are matched to the reading skill level of the target students and can be easily understood by the majority of the target learners. The literary texts are suited for these have the reading age (grade level) of 7.

Readability of a piece of text is one way of ensuring it is set at the right level for a student. The texts were selected not only because of the personal judgment of the researcher of the text in the context of students' abilities, needs, and interests but also because of its readability score.

Comments and Suggestions Offered by the Two Groups of Respondents to Improve the Developed Enhancement Materials in English

Here were the comments and suggestions offered by the two groups of respondents on the developed enhancement reading material in Grade 7 English.

The comments that were offered by the respondents on the developed enhancement reading material in English were: a. The topics are relevant and interesting for the students; b. Module is organized correctly and perfectly; c. It is well organized and is suited and effective for the needs of the learners; d. Activities are very good and it will surely make students more interested to participate and answer assessment; e. Very good set of activities; and f. This is helpful especially among students who need remediation.

The suggestions which were offered by the respondents on the developed enhancement reading material in Grade 7 English included: a. Use more images since this is intended for low grades; b. Have a follow up research about an effective reading material to be used and can easily be adapted by non-readers; c. Provide students with progress chart after each activity at the back of the material; d. Organize the reading text and activities according to its difficulty; and e. Use various illustrations to activate the learners' visual.

Conclusions

Based on the results of the study, the conclusions derived are the following:

The developed enhancement reading material in Grade 7 English is practical for actual use of English teachers in Grade 7 level.

The evaluations of the two groups of respondents on the developed enhancement reading material in Grade 7 English do not vary from each other.

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